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**D1.5 UPDATED
GUIDELINES FOR THE
BROADENING CITY-
REGIONS**

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HISTORY OF CHANGES, November 2025

Paragraph	Page	Changed
2.2 The CLIC framework	P8	Adjusted phrase: In the FoodCLIC Process (Figure 1), partners remain responsive and open to adapting to the needs and requests of the BCRs.
3.2 Guideline 2	P.21	Changed description of the role of the stakeholders: If not, you may invite the stakeholders you deem as more available to participate in a sense-making activity and support them to establish a Living Lab as a cooperative space.
3.2 Guideline 2	P.22	Reworded sentence: If you are unsure where to start when searching for food policies, you can begin by approaching three to five key informants who have been active in the city-region food system for a relatively long time (in governments, FPNs -including food councils and multi-stakeholder platforms -, NGOs working in food deprived and vulnerable neighbourhoods).
3.2 Guideline 2	P.24	Changed wording: Policy target group(s): the main societal groups that are directly affected by the policy.
3.2 Guideline 2	P.24	Explained monitoring tool: means of policy assessment and a preliminary establishment of an ambition for the food system to be achieved within a certain time horizon as the basis for the definition of a common vision for the same period. According to a set of indicators an Excel-based monitoring tool might be useful to keep track of the evolution towards a successful shift of the food system.
3.2 Guideline 2	P.27	Explained involvement of residents in participatory activities. Walking/Digital Surveys: These surveys involve local residents and are designed to capture their movement patterns within their neighbourhoods, identifying key food interaction points and understanding their daily food-related experiences.
All guidelines	P.22 (Links under Guideline 1) P. 25-26 (Links under Guideline 2) P. 30 (Links under Guideline 3)	Additions: In order to avoid providing extensive written guidance, useful links to training, practical tips on mapping food systems at national, city and neighbourhood levels, and analysis of the current state of policies and initiatives were added to the end of guidelines 1, 2 and 3. These tools are stored in the Public engagement toolkit of the CLEVERFOOD project. Regarding Figure 7 of D.1.6, it is unclear how to translate its contents into those of D.1.5. However, the links to training and practical tips provide users with a clearer idea of how to apply these guidelines.

1. FOODCLIC PROJECT CONTEXT

This document corresponds to “D1.5 - Updated guidelines for the extension city-regions” in the WP5, issued by Task 1.1. It is based on the experiences of the work led by the eight pilot European FoodCLIC Living Labs in WP2. The guidelines take into consideration the experiences and difficulties encountered by these Living Labs (LLs) that have implemented the first version of guidelines for mapping and gapping (D1.3) within WP2. After the mapping and gapping exercise, a survey has been answered by all LLs, in November 2023, and the results suggested principles of simplification and attention to practical aspects of the food system’s functioning in a specific real-life context.

On the other hand, according to the Broadening Plan (D5.6), the ambition of working with Broadening City Regions (BCRs) is to support them in their efforts to develop science, policy and society connections for the purpose of food system transformation grounded in local action in city-region food environments. The BCRs will proceed in a contextual basis, aiming to:

- 1. Draft a vision for their city-region food system;**
- 2. Create or strengthen a Food Policy Network (FPN) focusing on food policy, initiatives, and activities;**
- 3. Strengthen linkages with other city-regions;**
- 4. Support the development or implementation of a city-region food strategy integrated across scale (urban, peri-urban, rural) and sector (private, public, and civil society).**

For this to happen a set of exercises are proposed according to what the guidelines introduced in this document suggest:

- 5. Map or update a stakeholder map of actors working in the city-region food system;**
- 6. Map and analyse ongoing food policies, frameworks and initiatives in the city-region;**
- 7. Understand the structure of the city-region food system and causes of its unsustainability.**

Furthermore, FoodCLIC’s broadening approach is grounded in co-creation, a collaborative approach to engagement that allows stakeholders to develop inclusive and sustainable mechanisms for change. Figure 1 shows the process of FoodCLIC’s broadening approach and depicts the 10 steps that the BCRs are envisaged to go through. D1.5 provides guidelines, tools, and templates to facilitate the Step 3 – Stakeholder identification and mapping along with Step 5 – Analyse the current state of the city-region food system.

In the FoodCLIC Process (Figure 1), partners remain responsive and open to adapting to the needs and requests of the BCRs. ICLEI European Secretariat (ES) will be the point of contact for the five European Broadening city-regions and ICLEI African Secretariat (AS) will be the point of contact for

the three African city-regions. Together, ICLEI ES and AS with support from ICLEI World Secretariat and the entire FoodCLIC consortium will facilitate the implementation of this Broadening Plan.

Figure 1. FoodCLIC Phases and Process.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE GUIDELINES

2.1 INTRODUCTION

We consider ‘mapping’ to include a searchable compilation of information about, for example, initiatives, food policies, planning frameworks, food supply chain, food environments and food system actors, amongst others. Mapping goes beyond associating an experience or initiative with geographical coordinates on a cartographic map to convey spatial information. The guidelines developed for the mapping are meant to be used as common orientations for the eight BCRs to gather and systematize information concerning their food systems. However, there is enough flexibility for adjusting the methodology to accommodate indispensable specificities that might be justifiable for them to progress on a coherent basis. For instance, if city-regions have a good overview of their stakeholders, they could tread lightly there and focus more on other aspects. These adjustments should be discussed and articulated with the respective task leader and the WP1 and WP5 coordination as well as the project coordination when necessary. The BCR may also take advantage of the results from Task 2.1 and Task 2.2 regarding the literature review and the sample of Food Policy Networks (FPNs) interviewed worldwide and from outputs from Tasks 2.3, 2.4 and 2.5 (see Appendix D2.2, 2.3 and D2.5, respectively). The process of co-design of the real-life interventions run in the eight LLs coordinated by WP3 may also be useful in terms of lessons learned and providing inspiration for the BCRs to define an action plan (Step 8 of Figure 1) that might be put into action (Step 9 of Figure 1).

Therefore, the guidelines provide adapted guidance to support the mapping and gapping tasks in the eight BCRs. With them, the BCRs are supported to progress on the baseline assessment towards visioning, policymaking, planning and intervening to truly contribute towards inclusive food system transformation in the upcoming steps of the strategic planning (Steps 6 and 7 of Figure 1). This baseline assessment is composed of three different and complementary guidelines related to two steps (steps 3 and 5) of the FoodCLIC process:

Step 3. Stakeholder identification and mapping

This step refers to those who are active in pursuing food system transformation and what their interests, capacities and interactions are. The stakeholder map serves as a basis to analyse and address gaps and harmful power inequalities across and within actor networks. Mapping is

also, a way to include and listen to marginalised, food-deprived and vulnerable stakeholder groups whose knowledge and perspectives are typically excluded from policy-oriented mapping. It is also an acknowledgement of who is and was missing from food system research and governance processes with an intention to invite and collaborate with them on this project to create new partnerships to address blind spots. The mapping exercise involves ethical, evolving, and interactive mapping initiatives that are intended to be used to advance sustainable and just food systems.

Step 5. Analyse the current state of the city-region food system

The guidelines are to be used primarily by the practitioners of the BCRs that are involved in food systems' dynamics and initiatives and the coordination teams or focal points that are meant to support these local teams. They will be guided to set up or to complement data sets of eventual existing knowledge, especially concerning identifying and assessing current and upcoming urban food-related policies and planning frameworks, mapping stakeholders to identify networks and actors engaged with city-region food systems, their capacities and their relations and mapping the urban food environments and food systems. Other city-regions/FPNs or researchers can also make use of the separate tools for the purpose of stakeholder mapping and/or understanding the state of the current food system.

The guidelines for the food system baseline assessment should provide: (i) a common ground for each BCR to systematise information to better understand its contextual situation; (ii) stimulus to interact within the FPN operating in the respective food environments; and (iii) helpful foundations to co-design visions, inclusive integrated food policies, food-sensitive planning frameworks and real-life interventions. In the next sections, the primary concept of the CLIC framework is described, followed by a glossary as an overview of the essential concepts and definitions for the exercise of mapping and gapping.

2.2 THE CLIC FRAMEWORK

The CLIC framework is the primary conceptual basis where the project FoodCLIC is rooted as a central reference to the guidelines. The CLIC framework will guide policy-, planning- and practice-based interventions in urban food environments (and associated urban food systems) that deliver sustainable **Co-benefits**, strengthen rural-urban **Linkages**, enhance social **Inclusion** and create new **Connectivities** between food and other complex systems (see Figure 2). The CLIC is explicitly a normative framework; it outlines a direction of travel for food sustainability agendas by emphasizing four key dimensions of social, environmental, spatial and sectoral 'integration'. It also allows for comparative studies within the FoodCLIC project as well as monitoring and evaluating food system transformation along the project time horizon and beyond. Each of the elements of the framework is briefly explained below.

Figure 2 - The four pillars of the CLIC framework

C – Co-benefits: Interrelated economic, social and environmental objectives. It recognizes that sustainability strategies may create synergies and trade-offs.

L – Linkages: Creating or strengthening positive environmental, sociocultural and economic linkages between urban, peri-urban and rural areas and between land and sea.

I – Inclusion: Inclusion of all food system actors, while ensuring also a fairer distribution of its outcomes. It emphasises the role of knowledge pluralism (evidence-based, experimental and experiential) and the related different values (from socio-ecological justice to economic competitiveness)

C – Connectivities: The relationships between food and other policy priorities (e.g. climate change, resource scarcity, biodiversity conservation, sustainable transport, affordable housing and employment). Acknowledging the importance of connectivities is a fundamental step to start engaging with the rigidities, divides and gaps that have hampered the development of integrated food policies – that is, the fragmentation of responsibilities across multiple departments, ministries and state agencies, the asymmetries of power between food system actors and between levels of governance and the increasing corporate control exercised by agribusiness and transnational companies.

2.3 GLOSSARY

The exercise of mapping and gapping following common guidelines requires a conceptual baseline to ensure that all teams - the first eight LLs in the pilot city-regions plus the eight BCRs – are using the same terminology whilst characterizing and analysing each of the city-region food systems. Therefore, there are other fundamental concepts and definitions to take into consideration in each of the guidelines as summarised in Table 1. The source of information for this glossary came from the Description of the Action (DoA), as well as some of the results from the training sessions and some refinements to express the debate that has occurred in various interaction initiatives mostly in WP1.

Table 1- Concepts and definitions per Task guideline

TASK	CONCEPT AND DEFINITIONS
Guideline 1 Stakeholder identification and mapping	Stakeholders
	Multi-stakeholder groups
	Food Policy Network
	Quadruple helix
	Reciprocity
	Food-sensitive planning framework
	Initiatives to change urban food systems
Guideline 2 Analysis of the current state of food policies and initiatives in the city- region food system	Food system
	City-region food system (CRFS)
	Food policy
	Food Strategy
	Integrated food policies
	Food-related policies
	Urban planning framework
	Ecological (f)actors
Additional (f)actors	
Guideline 3 Analysis of the current state of the city-region food system	Food environment
	Deprived neighbourhood
	Food deprived and vulnerable groups

Food policy: A food policy is a strategic tool that explicitly covers the topic of food. In an ideal case, it includes a problem statement, a set of objectives and a concrete course of action (implementation action plan), using policy instruments (e.g., laws and (tax) regulations, (urban) land-use planning, investments and subsidy schemes, communication strategies, covenants, etc.) over time with a specified resource allocation. Policies can pertain to bodies of government (such as municipalities), but also to other food system stakeholders. For example, companies can also have food policies for their canteens or the foods they buy, process or sell as part of their business.

Food-related policies: Policies that engage with food (i.e. policies that mention food), but not as the main focus. Instead, the main focus might be climate, health, etc.

Integrated food policies: Policies that work along all four pillars of the **CLIC framework**, towards an ideal situation in which the policy: (i) realizes sustainability co-benefits; (ii) establishes linkages between urban and rural areas; (iii) includes all relevant food system stakeholders; and (iv) builds connections between food and other policy domains.

Urban planning framework: This concerns the organization of the physical, material or spatial elements of an urban area. In an ideal case, it comprises: (i) a plan (e.g. a strategic plan or vision plan) which articulates a clear vision for urban planning and has a long-term horizon intended to articulate the big picture ideas, goals, and principles; (ii) planning process, which establishes a clear process and mechanisms to support the interactions of public, private, and community sectors during the development and implementation of the plan; and (iii) planning regulations, which form the legal regime that frame the planning process (i.e., zoning laws and land-use plans). Examples may include, but are by no means limited to, regulations shaping access to land for (sustainable) agriculture, regulations on how and which public space can be used for food markets, regulations on fast food advertising and children's education, etc.

Food-sensitive planning framework: Most cities have one planning framework that addresses all domains/sectors in relation to spatial planning. Therefore, we are not looking for a planning framework specifically focused on food, but on a planning framework that includes food concerns, i.e. which is food-sensitive, by including food priorities in its framework/strategic/vision plan, and in its planning process stipulates processes and mechanisms to engage with questions around food in planning.

Initiatives to change urban food systems: These are initiatives or actions that produce changes to food environments in the cities and towns in the city-region, while also resulting in changes throughout the food system (e.g., the distribution channels, sites of production,

etc.). They are similar to “real-life interventions”, which are initiatives to change urban food systems undertaken as part of the FoodCLIC project (see below).

Real-life interventions: Experimental activities that produce changes to food environments in the cities and towns involved, which result in changes throughout the food system (e.g., the distribution channels, sites of production, etc.). These experimental activities may involve either first-time trials of a particular intervention in a city-region or the scaling-out of an on-going initiative at one location in the city-region to other locations in the city-region. The real-life interventions that FoodCLIC is seeking to implement, and scale will allow city-regions to fill gaps in their knowledge and build the evidence-base for policymaking and planning to realize food system transformation.

Food Policy Network (FPN): A FPN is a broad network of committed actors (individuals and organizations) that seek to collaborate and influence policy making to bring about food system transformation in an area. In FoodCLIC’s Deliverable 2.4 a wide variety of terms to indicate FPNs are listed, including Food Policy Council (FPC), Food Alliance, Coalition or Platform. In the African context the term Multi-stakeholder Platform (MSP) is often used. FPNs can be informal or formal, inside or outside government. FPNs have been proven to be a promising governance arrangement to sustain long-term multi-stakeholder engagement with food system transformation at a city-region level. The FPNs in FoodCLIC will initially operate based on a collective understanding of the city-region food system, a shared vision for the urban food environment and jointly performed analysis of good practices. Informed by this knowledge base, FPNs will formulate an integrated food strategy to make healthy and sustainable food an easy choice for all. Networking activities are recommended to enroll more government actors, CSOs, private actors, higher education institutions and research organisations towards an increase of FPN membership.

Food Strategy: The co-definition of a vision or inspiration to transform the food system in a systemic perspective by an engaged stakeholders established as an FPN and to steer subsequent learning from real-life interventions, the development of evidence-based and integrated urban food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks by municipalities and other relevant organizations. It may also correspond to a strategic instrument with a territorial and intersectoral basis, which explicitly covers the planning of food systems in a systemic way, pursuing the principles of spatial planning and territorial development and cohesion.

Quadruple helix: Framework for representing relations between different types of actors, most commonly used in the context of innovation economics and innovation policy. Quadruple helix actors are usually delineated as:

1. Government (e.g., municipalities, distinct departments or directorates within municipalities, municipal service providers, ministries, etc.)
2. Business & industry (e.g., (local) corporations, food entrepreneurs, farmers, etc.)
3. Civil society (e.g., Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), Community-Based Organizations (CBOs), organizations of food-deprived and vulnerable groups, etc.)
4. Research & education (e.g., research organisations, schools, higher education institutions (HEIs), such as universities (of applied science), etc.)

Ecological (f)actors; Beyond quadruple helix actors, the stakeholders in a FPN might also want to underscore relations they have with ecological actors or factors. E.g., the soil, the water, biodiversity and the air that are used and impacted on in agricultural production are examples of such ecological (f)actors, just like the soil's biodiversity, surface water's cleanliness or contamination levels and air pollution.

Additional (f)actors: Apart from quadruple helix and ecological (f)actors, there are also all sorts of other organizations, institutions, systems or structures that can be considered part of the actor network of LLs. E.g., transportation systems and infrastructure and (economic) policies (including e.g. (EU) agricultural subsidy schemes) can also be perceived as actors in the network, that make a difference with relation to the network's efficacy in realizing FoodCLIC's objectives.

Stakeholders: persons, groups, or organisations that are (1) affected by the project, (2) interested in the project, and/or (3) able to affect the project.

City-region food system (CRFS): "In general, the city region is understood as a given geographical region that includes one or more urban centres and their surrounding peri-urban and rural hinterland across which flows of people, food, goods, resources and ecosystem services are happening. A CRFS encompasses all food system actors and activities taking place in the city region and over which the local/regional government have planning and intervention powers".

Food environment: "The interface where people interact with the wider food system to acquire and consume food". FoodCLIC distinguishes six types: (i) retail food environment (e.g., supermarkets); (ii) hospitality food environment (e.g., restaurants); (iii) institutional food environment (e.g., school canteens, hospital meals, food banks); (iv) agri-food environment (e.g., community gardens, urban agriculture); (v) alternative & community food environment (e.g., community kitchens, food consumer cooperatives, park BBQs); and (vi) wild food environment (e.g., foraging herbs & fruits, fishing). Each has both physical and digital elements.

Deprived neighbourhood: This is a geographically bound area with a relatively high proportion of adults with low social economic status, as characterized by indicators such as unemployment, low income, low education and low-paying jobs, poor health, lack of infrastructures, climate vulnerability, etc.

Food-deprived and vulnerable groups: People whose diets are lacking in quantity or nutritional quality (resulting in food safety risks and undernutrition) on account of limited access because of spatiality (e.g., living in 'food deserts'), living on low income and/or personal circumstances (e.g., institutionalized persons, single-parent families).

3. MAPPING AND GAPPING GUIDELINES

The guidelines for mapping and gapping the BCR food systems are aligned with the guidelines defined formerly by WP1. They serve to simplify in a concise manner the WP5 tasks of mapping and gapping that new teams will engage in. It provides an integrated outlook on the interactions between the food environments and the actors who will be involved first in the mapping and gapping activities and second in the local initiatives that will take place. Each BCR should have a specific efficient time planning to run the different mapping and gapping activities and clarifying who is doing what at which point in time, who are the target groups that can provide useful information for more than one task, and who will analyse and store the results of the mapping and gapping. To make the process as efficient as possible, see where your activities can be coupled together, to obtain more information whilst avoid approaching the same person on multiple occasions.

Table 2 provides a quick overview of the main aim of each tool, the expected outputs and what the results of mapping and gapping may flow into, in terms of workflow. To accomplish each BCR objective, each city-region must identify a coordinator, organise or strengthen a FPN and, whenever possible, find a research partner.

Table 2 – Overview of each of the guidelines

Guideline	WHAT DOES THE ACTIVITY BRING YOU?	WHAT WILL THE RESULTS SUPPORT?
Guideline 1 - Stakeholder identification and mapping (STEP 3 of the FoodCLIC process – Figure 1)	Answer the questions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who are the key stakeholders? • How are they engaging in the CRFS? • What are the strengths and weaknesses in the capacities of different stakeholder groups to contribute to the design and implementation of integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks? • Barriers that FPNs will need to overcome and associated learning needs of FPNs. 	Nourishing the longer-term (multi-year) processes of policy and planning transformation, FoodCLIC directs special attention to the potentials for new and enhanced relationships between different stakeholder groups. Such relationships are a vital starting point for co-designing an innovative action plan in (urban) food environments that bring about wider changes (e.g., policy and planning) in the CRFS.
Guideline 2 - Analyse the current state of policies and initiatives in the city-region (local) food system	An overview of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food policies, planning frameworks and initiatives on food in your city-region; • Gaps and leverage points for food system transformation in key existing and upcoming policies, planning 	Strengthening an understanding of the CRFS; Gathering fundamental information to strengthen and develop integrated food policies and planning frameworks to support the co-design of future food initiatives.

(STEP 5 of the FoodCLIC process – Figure 1)	frameworks and initiatives in your city-region and at national level	
Guideline 3 - Analyse the current state of the city-region (local) food system (STEP 5 of the FoodCLIC process – Figure 1)	<p>An overview of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food production and consumption in the CRFS; • The neighbourhoods with relatively large communities of food deprived and vulnerable people with whom we map, co-design and implement local action plans; • Power relations affecting urban food environments in deprived areas and disconnecting them from CRFS. 	<p>Strengthening an understanding of the CRFS; Gathering fundamental information to strengthen current initiatives and co-design new interventions to enhance the sustainability of the food system</p>

3.1 GUIDELINE 1 – STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION AND MAPPING

GUIDELINE 1: STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION AND MAPPING (STEP 3 of the FoodCLIC Process, Figure 1)

Each BCR will perform an actor analysis and mobilise stakeholders to strengthen or develop the structure of a multi-stakeholder body for food initiatives (comprising practitioners from civil society and private parties, policymakers, planners, and researchers). Relevant insights, lessons learned and good practices from within FoodCLIC will be identified and analysed.

Mapping and gapping the stakeholders of a food system consists of (i) identifying key entities, groups or individuals who intervene significantly in the food system and (ii) building a common ground for longer-term collaboration. The objective is to learn more about the food system you will intervene in and to identify which kind of interactions among stakeholders may contribute to design food strategies that can be implemented into policy and planning actions in a later stage.

The purpose of a mapping and gapping exercise is thus to obtain a preliminary framework to characterize the stakeholders' dynamics and to better understand to what extent there is a common systemic understanding on how the food system operates. In case this perception would be shared

by most of the stakeholders (for instance in case that most of them would be already organized in an FPN), it may accelerate the collaborative process. In case many divergences are encountered, there is a need for a time frame to build the conditions to enable a shared perspective on the food system.

This guideline consists of three interlinked stages:

- First, identifying the main stakeholders in the food system and understanding how they interact
- Second, gaining insight into stakeholders' perception of the food system, their expectations and needs along with their readiness to participate in a common action plan.
- Third, understanding power dynamics and identifying the gaps that may constraint the establishment of future collaborative and systemic action.

STAGE 1 – Stakeholders' identification

To identify the stakeholders in the city-region food system, it is recommended to conduct key-informant interviews. It is important to apply the quadruple helix framework to ensure 'equal' representation in views/stakeholders that can be brought to the table. To use the quadruple helix framework that refers to the actors most involved in innovation economics and policies, you may consider:

1. **Government and public sector:** including politicians and civil servants (e.g., in spatial planning, health programmes) on municipal and provincial scales as well as ministerial offices that have substantial power over the CRFS – ministry of environment, agriculture, health, immigration etc.; municipalities, distinct departments or directorates within municipalities, municipal service providers, ministries, etc.)
2. **Research and education:** including universities, colleges, research organisations, think tanks and other knowledge institutes. Try to have representation across multiple disciplines (e.g., urban planning, public health, sociology, environmental science, political science, etc.) with relevant specialisations and city-region experiences. (e.g., research organisations, schools, higher education institutions (HEIs), such as universities (of applied science), etc.
3. **Civil society:** including diverse groups with different perspectives on food system transformation, like citizen groups, social movements, NGOs, community and faith-based organisations (CBOs & FBOs) as well as media, art and cultural organizations/institutions who engage with food to improve wellbeing, health sustainability and generate systemic changes (e.g., Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), Community Based Organizations (CBOs), organizations of food-deprived and vulnerable groups, etc.)
4. **Business and industry:** including agri-food and retail corporations, food consumer cooperatives, small and medium-sized enterprises, industrial or sustainable farms (e.g. (local) corporations, food entrepreneurs, farmers, etc.).

For each stakeholder, you may fill in the template below, which can be adjusted according to your specific context and needs. Try to identify at least four relevant stakeholders for each segment of the quadruple helix:

Table 3 – Stakeholders’ mapping

STAKEHOLDER’S NAME	MAIN ACTIVITY (BY EACH QUADRUPLE HELIX GROUP)	SCALE OF ACTION (REGIONAL, MUNICIPAL, NEIGHBOURHOODS)	WAY OF ACTING (NETWORK, COMMUNITY, INDEPENDENTLY, OTHER)
Stakeholder a)			
Stakeholder b)			
(...)			

STAGE 2 – Stakeholders’ engagement

Next it is important you gain insight into stakeholders’ perception of the food system, their expectations and needs along with their readiness to participate in a common action plan. To this end, you will most likely conduct semi-structured or informal interviews with stakeholders. In case an FPN already exists in your city-region you may start by interlinking with them bearing in mind its progressive enlargement and consistency enhancement. If not, you may invite the stakeholders you deem as more available to participate in a sense-making activity and support them to establish a Living Lab as a cooperative space. The interaction may provide insights into what collaborative relations and capacity sharing they may encounter to set up a strategic positive intervention in the food system they are acting in.

STAGE 3 – Identification of power dynamics and main gaps

To complete this stakeholder identification and mapping exercise it is important to better understand the ways stakeholders interact with one another, their capacities and particularly the power relations between them. To this end, it is recommendable to include a stakeholder event that includes interactive sessions with different stakeholders in the city-region food system. The mapping activities in themselves are a step towards reconnections and new coalitions, plus a great way to introduce stakeholders to FoodCLIC’s cross-scalar and inclusive approach to food system transformation. The interactive session should respond to the following questions:

- What do you give and receive from other stakeholder groups?
- How can relations improve for food system transformation?
- What capacities are needed from yourself and other stakeholder groups to improve relations and transform their city-region food system?

The information from stages 1 and 2 and the stakeholder event, will give insights into which stakeholders are missing (the gaps), but who are expected to be relevant for the food system to work in an effective dynamic and to provide healthy and sustainable local food. Which stakeholder group is missing will depend on the local context.

The mapping and gapping activities are expected to generate direct benefits translated into the ability to build trust for a common objectives definition and share responsibilities on a strategic and action commitments for an active system-transforming collaboration and social learning at subsequent phases of the FoodCLIC process

For reference to several user cases (the eight pilot city-regions), we refer to D2.3 - [Report on maps of local stakeholders in the eight city-regions](#)

The following links offer more practical guidance and training on stakeholder identification and mapping. These tools were prepared in collaboration with the *CLEVERFOOD* project:

Mapping Out Food Systems – What, Who, How of Your Food System

Stakeholder analysis: <https://food2030.eu/toolkit/stakeholder-analysis/>

Mapping food systems at national and city-regional level: <https://food2030.eu/toolkit/city-region-food-systems-and-food-environments/>

Template Stakeholder Analysis:

<https://food2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/Template-stakeholder-analysis.pdf>

3.2 GUIDELINE 2 - ANALYSE THE CURRENT STATE OF POLICIES AND INITIATIVES IN THE CITY-REGION FOOD SYSTEM

GUIDELINE 2 – ANALYSE THE CURRENT STATE OF THE POLICIES AND INITIATIVES IN THE CITY-REGION FOOD SYSTEM

(STEP 5 of the FoodCLIC Process, Figure 1)

Each BCR builds a joint understanding of relevant existing and upcoming (local, regional and national) policies on food and adjacent policy-domains and planning developments (including newly planned or regeneration of urban areas) of governmental actors, as well as other initiatives undertaken by stakeholders.

The transformation of the city-region's food systems that FoodCLIC aims to undertake requires an understanding of existing and upcoming food policies, planning frameworks and initiatives. This may be done over three stages along with the description of the geographical and political context in which it has been designed and implemented.

STAGE 1 – Developing an inventory of food policies, strategies, planning frameworks and food initiatives

If you are unsure where to start when searching for food policies, you can begin by approaching three to five key informants who have been active in the city-region food system for a relatively long time (in governments, FPNs -including food councils and multi-stakeholder platforms -, NGOs working in food deprived and vulnerable neighbourhoods).

Then, engage with the selected key-informants through long (±two-hour) semi-structured interviews, with the help of a large map of the city-region, pencils, pens and markers as well as sticky notes (or other creative means). You can ask the informants to share with you their insights and observations, as well as beliefs, hunches and frustrations along the lines of relevant policies, planning frameworks, food initiatives and stakeholders' part of the city-region food system. This way, a comprehensive view on the development of the city-regional food system (both mapping and gapping) can be obtained. The key-informants can connect you to their networks, which may be able to fill in some of the gaps identified. This 'snowballing' approach may also allow you to rapidly diversify your network.

After this first inventory, some desk research is recommended to complete your inventory of present and upcoming food policies. This may be easily accessible through websites (of organizations that issue such policies, including bodies of government, companies, public institutions, etc.) that may be developed by national, provincial/regional, city or neighbourhood-level bodies of government.

Table 4 – Present and upcoming food policies inventory

STAGE 1 - PRESENT & UPCOMING FOOD POLICIES INVENTORY				
Policy name	Level of government/ geographical focus of the policy (National, Provincial/Regional, City, Neighbourhood)	Name of body of government/ organization & department	Name & brief description of the policy	Runtime of the policy

STAGE 2 – Characterising the targets and governance of each food policy

From the list of food policies that have been identified in Stage 1, you should select the ones that interact more actively on the transformation of the food system of your city region and go deeper on their targets and governance that frames the decision-making process.

Table 5 – Selection of food policies that actively transform the food system

STAGE 2 – SELECTION OF FOOD POLICIES THAT ACTIVELY TRANSFORM THE FOOD SYSTEM					
Policy name	Policy goal	Policy instrument	Policy target group	Ultimate beneficiary	Ranking (1 to 3)

Policy goal: statements describing the fundamental outcomes that a policy aims to achieve through its activities. Policy goals are high order statements of desired outcomes (e.g. reduced environmental impact).

Policy instrument: techniques or means through which public actors (e.g. national and EU government bodies, public agencies, etc.) attempt to attain their goals.

Policy target group(s): the main societal groups that are directly affected by the policy.

Ultimate beneficiary: the societal group that is linked to the overall policy goal (e.g. a sugar tax affects manufacturing companies but is intended to promote healthy eating habits among consumers, who thus are the ultimate beneficiaries).

Complementary, in Step 2 you may understand the governance of the selected food policies as the “*steering and co-ordination of interdependent (usually collective) actors based on institutionalised rule systems*” that are responsible for the policy implementation. In other words, this notion refers to the interactions and implementation issues across policy levels, and the management of the context in which such interactions take place. This entails a shift towards the adoption of a systemic perspective that considers the interrelatedness of the whole food chain and cycle. Our suggestion is to analyse whether governance occurs horizontally (i.e. those policies that address multiple policy goals and/or target multiple policy actors) or vertically in case they are built on interactions across scales between public and/or private entities aiming at the realisation of collective goals).

In case some objectives for the food system transformation are already established, a ranking perspective could be useful as an opportunity to debate how each of the selected policies might be relevant to reach the goals and ambition for a transformative shift. If that would be the case, you may fill the last column of Table 5 using a scale from 1 to 3, where 1 means slightly active, 2 means active and 3 means very active.

STAGE 3 – Gaps and barriers for the success of food system transformation in key existing and upcoming food policies

To identify gaps and barriers implies a more analytical and critical basis that may combine the expectations the FPN may have regarding the ambition for the food system transformation with the assessment of resources and capabilities that might exist in real life context to convert policy orientations and recommendations into action. It implies means of policy assessment and a preliminary establishment of an ambition for the food system to be achieved within a certain time horizon as the basis for the definition of a common vision for the same period. According to a set of indicators an Excel-based monitoring tool might be useful to keep track of the evolution towards a successful shift of the food system.

For reference to several user cases (the eight pilot city-regions), we refer to D2.2 [Report on food-related policies and planning frameworks and initiatives in the eight city-regions and at national level](#)

The following links offer more practical guidance and training on analysing the current state of policies and initiatives in the city-region food system. These tools were prepared in collaboration with the *CLEVERFOOD* project:

[Designing a multi-stakeholder and multi-level strategic plan for food system transformation](#)

Objectives for engaging stakeholders

- Stakeholder engagement in food system transformation feeds into distinct objectives.
- Visioning and Planning follows the System and Stakeholder Mapping stage, and is a prerequisite for Experimentation. This stage helps food initiatives:
 - Set a shared direction
 - Build ownership and direction

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Analyzing food policies and initiatives: <https://food2030.eu/toolkit/integrated-food-policies-and-initiatives/>

3.3 GUIDELINE 3 – ANALYSE THE CURRENT STRUCTURE OF THE CITY-REGION FOOD SYSTEM

GUIDELINE 3 – ANALYSE THE CURRENT STRUCTURE OF THE CITY-REGION FOOD SYSTEM (STEP 5 of the FoodCLIC Process, Figure 1)

Each BCR builds a joint understanding of the food environment and interrelated food systems in each city-region, through the analysis of data on food production, food supply chains, food environments (retail, hospitality, agri-food, institutional, etc.), rural-urban linkages, consumer behaviour and food-deprived neighbourhoods.

Any identification, selection and design of interventions in city-regions food environments should start with a thorough understanding of the current city-regions food system (CRFS), which includes the system's structural features, and an understanding of the causes of unsustainability. In the

pursuit of understanding urban food environments and their intricate connections with the CRFSs, the FoodCLIC project has adopted a comprehensive and participatory approach. This methodology is designed to be both inclusive and exhaustive, ensuring that the research captures the nuances of the food environment from various perspectives. This guideline is structured around three stages:

- measuring the impacts and changes,
- identifying and mapping neighbourhoods, and
- understanding power relations.

By mapping these features, a comprehensive understanding of the CRFS can be created, as the activities focus on the outline of the current system, but also pinpoint systemic gaps. Interventions can target these gaps as systemic leverage points. The analyses can be part of a baseline and endline study in order to keep track of progress when implementing interventions. Below each of the stages is elaborated.

STAGE 1 – Measuring impacts and changes

The initial step in this journey is to establish a foundational understanding of the CRFS. To construct a holistic picture of the CRFS you need to collect data on: agricultural inputs, agricultural land use, energy consumption, livestock, species, and respective manure management systems, production of crops and livestock products, food demand, waste and losses, and import and export. Data can come from both primary and secondary sources. When city-regional data is unavailable, it may be worthwhile to scale provincial, regional or national level data, considering the share of agricultural land area of the city region on the total (e.g. using Corine Land Cover 2018 (CLC, 2018)). The food demand of the city-regions can be obtained by scaling down data on the national food demand derived from FAOSTAT (FAO, 2023). In addition, the amount of food produced within the city-region can be estimated, comparing data on agricultural production with the food needed to feed the population within the city-region. This gives an idea of the share of inhabitants that can be fed with local food produced in each city region.

STAGE 2 – Identifying and mapping neighbourhoods

As the research progresses, you need to shift the focus to a more granular level, specifically targeting neighbourhoods with significant populations of food-deprived and vulnerable individuals. The aim is not just to identify these areas but to actively engage with them. The process of mapping the different neighbourhoods, as well as engaging with the local inhabitants requires several different methodological steps. The section below describes the important parameters you are asked to use to identify and map the neighbourhoods. At first a city-regional perspective is taken where the vulnerabilities, resources and opportunities regarding the CRFS are explored. The elements are specific dimensions relevant to understanding the local context of each city-region. They capture the momentum and trends that are important to consider when discussing the CRFS in place. After that, through income, health and food security related data a better understanding is

generated of the population and their whereabouts. A Multi-Criteria Analysis based on this data then gives a number of highlighted neighbourhoods which potentially house the target group for FoodCLIC. All these steps help in coming from a birds-eye city-regional view towards a neighbourhood orientation, which then sets the stage for co-creative interaction with local stakeholders to better understand the food environment and help with generating subsequent maps and figures.

1. Vulnerabilities, resources and opportunities

We recommend producing a minimum of three distinct maps, each focusing on a specific aspect of the CRFS: vulnerabilities, resources, and opportunities. These maps help you to pinpoint what is considered important about the CRFS by relevant actors, but also to highlight what is often overlooked.

- The **vulnerabilities map** aims to highlight areas or aspects of the food system that were susceptible to challenges, be they environmental, economic, or social. This could range from regions with scarce food resources to areas prone to environmental risks or social vulnerabilities such as required levels of food aid.
- The **resources map** illuminates the strengths and assets of the CRFS. This could encompass agricultural land use, highlighting regions abundant in food production, or areas with a rich diversity of food environments, from institutional to wild.
- The **opportunities map** is forward-looking, pinpointing areas with transformative potential. It can spotlight regions ripe for sustainable agricultural practices or zones where food strategies are being actively developed.

Various different types of maps and figures can be constructed based on what is most relevant and available for the particular CRFS.

2. Income levels, food insecurity and health statistics

In the complex journey of understanding urban food environments and their interplay with CRFS, it is important to delve deeper into the spatial dimensions of food insecurity, income disparities, and health outcomes. We strongly recommend developing several maps to visualize the complexities of the food environment on a neighbourhood scale, allowing for a more targeted approach in addressing food-related challenges. To begin with, three distinct maps can be generated to show the distribution of income, food insecurity and obesity levels on a neighbourhood scale for the entire city-region to identify food-deprived areas with a high need for interventions to access healthy and sustainable food. These maps can be constructed using an adapted version of Simón-Rojo's (2021) method of a compound index. This method combines criteria of average income, food insecurity, and childhood obesity, and provides both a visual representation of these criteria and detailed descriptions, offering context and insights into the data.

3. Multi-Criteria Analysis

Following this, a Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) map can be generated, integrating the three aforementioned datasets into one comprehensive visual. This map is instrumental in identifying neighbourhoods with significant proportions of food-deprived and vulnerable groups. The MCA

provides insights into potential areas of interest based on a combination of quantitative data and qualitative information. Such areas, characterized by their 'fertile complexity', indicate a strong social fabric, and are deemed favourable for connecting pre-existing civil society networks with municipal programs.

The next step in FoodCLIC's methodology involves zooming in on at least two of the neighbourhoods identified through the MCA. These neighbourhoods are further explored based on their transformative potential, considering factors such as the presence of local networks, free food distribution centres, social organizations, community food gardens, municipal markets, and public kitchens. The aim is to understand underlying dynamics in these neighbourhoods and identify opportunities for real-life interventions.

4. Mapping Exercise

Through mapping exercises, co-design sessions, and taking part in various local events, you can identify tangible improvements in these communities. Various participatory mapping methods can be employed. We have selected four of these methods based on their ability to integrate local knowledge in a dynamic and creative manner, mobilizing diverse stakeholders and ensuring that the research is grounded in the lived experiences and needs of the community:

- **Walking/Digital Surveys:** These surveys involve local residents and are designed to capture their movement patterns within their neighbourhoods, identifying key food interaction points and understanding their daily food-related experiences. **Focus Groups with Neighbourhood Maps:** These sessions facilitate discussions around the food environment, using neighbourhood maps as visual aids. Residents can pinpoint specific areas of interest, share experiences, and provide context to the mapped data.
- **Transect Walks with PhotoVoice Mapping:** This method combines observational walks with the power of photography. As participants traverse their neighbourhoods, they capture images that represent their food environment, offering a visual narrative that complements the quantitative data.
- **Digital Crowdsourcing Mapping:** Leveraging the power of technology, this method allows residents to digitally mark and describe food-related points of interest within their neighbourhoods, creating a collaborative map that reflects the collective knowledge of the community.

FoodCLIC's pilot city-regions usually used two out of the four methods.

The data gathered through these participatory methods can then be used to generate a series of maps, each visualizing specific elements of the food environment. These elements can include the availability and density of different food spaces (ranging from food growing areas to retailing and food aid organizations), the accessibility of green spaces, socio-economic profiles of the local population, housing types, and transport routes. These maps can serve as a visual representation of the intricate interplay between various factors that influence food access and choices within urban neighbourhoods. In essence, these methodologies are a useful blend of participatory methods, data visualization, and in-depth analysis, providing a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of urban

food environments at the neighbourhood level, setting the stage for targeted interventions and sustainable food planning.

STAGE 3 – Understanding power relations

Understanding the physical layout of the food environment is just one piece of the puzzle. It is also important to delve deep into the underlying power dynamics that shape these environments. This third step begins with the engagement of at least eight key stakeholder groups, each offering a unique perspective on the food environment. These groups should represent a broad spectrum of actors involved in the CRFS, such as, representatives of food-deprived and vulnerable people, local food producers, food aid organizations, food-related policymakers and urban planners, food entrepreneurs, and additional groups chosen strategically, such as health professionals or local schools. By engaging with a diverse set of stakeholders the complex web of power relations that often lead to unhealthy or exclusive food environments is to be unravelled.

To this end, we advise to use the 'Power Tree of Healthy Food Access'. This group interview technique is designed to shed light on the root causes of unhealthy food environments and potential solutions to address them. Stakeholders are encouraged to discuss and debate, leading to insights into the challenges and opportunities within the urban food environment. Each group interview, ideally conducted in person, revolves around the Power Tree of Healthy Food Access, addressing three core questions:

- What makes a neighbourhood food environment unhealthy or exclusive?
- What are the disempowering roots of unhealthy or exclusive food environments?
- How can we make healthy and sustainable food accessible to all?

The stem of the tree is covered by the first question whereas the answers to the second question are visualized by the roots of the tree. The last question, regarding the solutions, got a place amongst the branches and leaves. More especially for the third question the participants are asked to list already existing solutions, ideal solutions and dream solutions.

For reference to several user cases (the eight pilot city-regions), we refer to D2.5 - [Report on maps of city-regional food system and urban food environments in deprived areas](#)

The following links offer more practical guidance and training on analysing the current structure of the city-region food system. These tools were prepared in collaboration with the *CLEVERFOOD* project:

CLEVERFOOD toolkit for engagement: <https://food2030.eu/toolkit-for-engagement/>
Mapping food systems at the neighbourhood level:
<https://food2030.eu/toolkit/mappingfoodsystems/>

4. APPENDICES

D1.1 – GUIDELINES FOR THE MAPPING EXERCISES IN WP2

This deliverable introduces a set of five groups of guidelines for mapping and analyzing good practices, food policy networks, food policies and planning frameworks, food systems and food environments to be used in tasks of the WP2 (T2.1-2.5), including the templates (informed by the CLIC framework) for secondary data analysis of scientific articles, reports, documents, social media and existing databases, as well as for targeted interviews with key food system stakeholders. The objective of these guidelines is to allow understanding on what is happening in the Living Lab food systems of each of the eight city-regions of the FoodCLIC project and identify gapping as the steps that may help to realize desired food system transformation.

The guidelines will provide the LL teams (i) a common ground for each city-region to systematize information to better understand its contextual situation; (ii) stimulus to interact within the Food Policy Networks operating in the food environment of each city-region; (iii) helpful foundations to co-design visions, inclusive integrated food policies, planning frameworks and real-life interventions. Some of them will be used by research teams to revise literature whilst others guide LL teams to gather and analyze fundamental information to operate the food system transformation through the development of sustainable co-benefits that might be useful not only for the project consortium but also to other city-regions across Europe and beyond.

[Guidelines for the mapping excersises.pdf \(FoodCLIC deliverable 1.1, not public\)](#)

D2.2 - REPORT ON FOOD-RELATED POLICIES AND PLANNING FRAMEWORKS AND INITIATIVES IN THE EIGHT CITY-REGIONS AND AT NATIONAL LEVEL

This report is the outcome of Task 2.3 (Work Package 2), which aims to identify and assess current and upcoming urban food-related policies, planning frameworks and initiatives to change city-regions' food systems. It also aims to spark transformative discussions and shed light on the significance of city-regions in driving food system transformation, emphasising the crucial role of (various forms of) Food Policy Networks (FPNs) in fostering sustainable, resilient, and equitable urban food systems. This report also examines how eight city-regions address gaps and identify leverage points for transforming their local food systems. To this end, the report showcases a selection of food-related policies, planning frameworks, and initiatives with high potential for food system transformation, including their contribution to the establishment of FPNs and strengthening city-region food systems. In order to analyse the extent to which policies, planning frameworks and initiatives contribute to systemic change, the report uses the CLIC conceptual framework.

[Report on food-related policies and planning frameworks and initiatives in the eight city-regions and at national level \(FoodCLIC deliverable 2.2\)](#)

D2.3 – REPORT ON MAPS OF LOCAL STAKEHOLDERS IN THE EIGHT CITY-REGIONS

This deliverable describes the output of Task 2.4 (WP 2), which entailed mapping local stakeholders to identify engaged networks and actors within city-regional food systems (CRFSs), as well as their capacities, activities, and relationships. The activities have been carried out from February until July 2023, in the Living Labs operating in eight city-regions, namely: Aarhus (Denmark), Amsterdam (the Netherlands), Barcelona (Spain), Berlin (Germany), Braşov (Romania), Budapest (Hungary), Lisbon (Portugal) and the Plain of Lucca (Italy).

The purpose of this document is to provide guidance to Living Labs and their partners aiming to enhance or establish their Food Policy Networks (FPNs) by:

- Providing a basic inventory of the variety of actors, and related activities, currently or potentially involved in FPNs in the eight city-regions;
- Identifying their main relations, capacities, and limitations; and
- Providing an overview of the actors' motivations for engaging in FPNs.

[Report on maps of local stakeholders in the eight city-regions \(FoodCLIC deliverable 2.3\)](#)

D2.5 - REPORT ON MAPS OF CITY-REGIONAL FOOD SYSTEM AND URBAN FOOD ENVIRONMENTS IN DEPRIVED AREAS

Task 2.5 is about mapping urban food environments and food systems, and through that is a pivotal task within the FoodCLIC project. It focuses on the participatory mapping and analysis of food environments in various urban neighbourhoods in the participating eight city-regions. Simultaneously in the eight city-regions: 1). Aarhus (Denmark), 2). Amsterdam (the Netherlands), 3). Barcelona (Spain), 4). Berlin (Germany), 5). Brasov (Romania), 6). Budapest (Hungary), 7). Lisbon (Portugal) and 8). Lucca (Italy) the Living Lab Teams engage with the primary objective of this task, which is to identify areas with significant proportions of food-deprived and vulnerable groups of people. FoodCLIC aims to have its result benefit for at least 50% people who are considered to suffer the most from the current food system. For that reason, this deliverable is drafted as it enables the eight Living Lab Teams to map and engage with food deprived and vulnerable groups within their food environment.

[Report on maps of city-regional food system and urban food environments in deprived areas \(FoodCLIC deliverable 2.5\)](#)

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